

Composition and Formation Constants of Binary and Ternary Complexes of Zinc(II) with γ -Picoline and Citraconic Acid

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A number of research papers¹⁻³ have been published on polarographic study of Zn^{II} complexes, though little attention has been paid on the use of γ -picoline⁴ and citraconic acid⁵ as ligands. In continuation to our previous work⁶, this paper presents the stoichiometry and formation constants of Zn^{II} - γ -picoline-citraconate system.

Experimental

Stock solutions of Zn^{II} (0.01 M), γ -picoline (0.2, 0.05 M), citraconic acid (disodium salt) (0.05 M) and supporting electrolyte potassium (2 M) were prepared in CO_2 -free double-distilled water. Experimental sets for polarography were prepared by keeping the concentration of Zn^{II} and KCl fixed at 1 mM and 0.1 M, respectively, with variation of ligand concentration in each set for the study of binary systems, whereas ternary systems were studied by keeping the concentration of one ligand fixed and changing that of the other.

Current-voltage curves were obtained on a C.I.C. (Baroda, India) automatic pen recording polarograph. The capillary used had the following characteristics: $m=2.37$ mg s^{-1} , $t=3.05s$ at 35 cm effective height of mercury column ($m^{2/3} t^{1/3} = 2.136$ mg^{2/3} s^{-1/2}). pH studies were done on a Elico LI-120 digital pH-meter and adjusted to the required value, i.e. 6.6 ± 0.02 by the addition of necessary amount of dilute HCl/NaOH solutions. All the operations were made at room temperature ($25 \pm 0.5^\circ$). Pure nitrogen gas was bubbled through the test solutions before recording the polarograms.

Results and Discussion

Zn^{II} as well as its complexes give well defined, diffusion-controlled reduction waves with reversible nature which is evident by the linear plots of i_a vs $\sqrt{h}$ and log plot slope values of 30 ± 2 mV, respectively.

Binary systems: Values of change in half-wave potential when plotted against the logarithm of ligand concentration, smooth curves were obtained (separately with each ligand) which indicated the formation of more than one complex species in each system. Stoichiometry and formation constant studies were therefore done by the method of Deford and Hume⁷. Tables 1 and 2 show the values of polarographic functions and other related data. Three binary complexes with each of the two ligands (γ -picoline and citraconic acid) were revealed with the formation constants as, Zn^{II} -citraconate: $\log \beta_{10}=2.65$, $\log \beta_{20}=3.90$, $\log \beta_{30}=5.64$; Zn^{II} - γ -picoline: $\log \beta_{01}=2.44$, $\log \beta_{02}=2.70$, $\log \beta_{03}=4.60$.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF F_j [Y] FUNCTIONS OF Zn^{II} - γ -PICOLINE SYSTEM

$Zn^{II} = 1.0$ mM, $\mu = 0.1$ M (KCl), pH = 6.6 ± 0.02 , Temp. = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$, $(E_{1/2})_0 = -1.10$ V vs SCE

Sl. no.	Concn. of γ -picoline M	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	i_a div	F_0 [Y]	F_1 [Y]	F_2 [Y] $\times 10^{-2}$	F_3 [Y] $\times 10^{-2}$
1.	0.00	-1.100	48	—	—	—	—
2.	0.01	-1.112	46	2.662	166.20	—	—
3.	0.02	-1.124	43	7.268	313.40	16.70	—
4.	0.03	-1.132	40	14.590	453.00	57.66	1.75
5.	0.04	-1.140	40	27.250	656.25	94.06	2.22
6.	0.05	-1.148	39	52.180	1 023.80	148.72	2.87

$\beta_1 = 280$, $\beta_2 = 500$, $\beta_3 = 40 000$; $\log \beta_1 = 2.44$, $\log \beta_2 = 2.70$, $\log \beta_3 = 4.60$.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF F_i [X] FUNCTIONS OF Zn^{II} -CITRACONATE SYSTEM

$Zn^{II} = 1.0$ mM, $\mu = 0.1$ M (KCl), pH = 6.6 ± 0.02 , Temp. = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$, $(E_{1/2})_0 = -1.10$ V vs SCE, $i_a = 48$

Sl. no.	Concn. of citraconate ion M	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	i_a div.	F_0 [X]	F_1 [X]	F_2 [X] $\times 10^{-2}$	F_3 [X] $\times 10^{-2}$
1.	0.00	-1.100	48	—	—	—	—
2.	0.01	-1.220	42	6.37	536.6	86.60	—
3.	0.02	-1.131	42	12.85	592.5	71.25	—
4.	0.03	-1.144	41	36.33	1 177.6	242.53	5.4
5.	0.04	-1.152	40	69.52	1 713.0	315.75	5.8
6.	0.05	-1.156	35	108.60	2 152.0	340.40	5.2

$\beta_1 = 450$, $\beta_2 = 8 000$, $\beta_3 = 40 000$; $\log \beta_1 = 2.65$, $\log \beta_2 = 3.90$, $\log \beta_3 = 5.64$.

Ternary systems: To evaluate the composition and formation constants of ternary complexes of Zn^{2+} in citraconate- γ -picoline mixed media, the concentration of γ -picoline was fixed at two values, so that one and two moles of γ picoline per Zn^{2+} mole exist in Zn^{2+} - γ -picoline media. This was actually afforded by keeping the concentration of γ -picoline fixed at 0.1 and 0.2 M and preparing two series of experimental sets with varying citraconate concentration. On recording the polarograms with the experimental sets, it was observed that the shift in $E_{1/2}$ values is more than that observed with binary systems. This indicates the formation of ternary complexes in solution. The Schaap and McMasters⁶ method was used to calculate polarographic functions, and constants A, B, C and D (Tables 3 and 4). The data reveal the formation of

tendency of a ligand to add to a complex and to substitute another ligand has been given (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F_{ij} [XY] FUNCTIONS OF Zn^{2+} - CITRACONATE - γ -PICOLINE MIXED SYSTEM

$Zn^{2+} = 1.0 \text{ mM}$, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (KCl), $\text{pH} = 6.6 \pm 0.02$, $\text{Temp.} = 25 \pm 0.5^\circ$,
 $(E_{1/2})_s = -1.10 \text{ V vs SCE}$, $i_d = 48$, γ -Picoline = 0.1 M (Fixed)

Sl. no.	Concn. of citraconate ion M	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	i_d div.	F_{00} [XY]	F_{10} [XY]	F_{20} [XY] $\times 10^{-2}$	F_{30} [XY] $\times 10^{-5}$
1.	0.01	-1.125	40	8.45	-	-	-
2.	0.02	-1.142	40	31.85	1 092.5	-	-
3.	0.03	-1.156	39	97.43	2 914.0	53.81	11.93
4.	0.04	-1.162	36	168.70	3 967.5	66.68	12.17
5.	0.05	-1.168	32	303.10	5 862.0	91.24	14.64

$A = 10, B = 1\ 300, C = 18\ 000, D = 100\ 000.$

TABLE 4—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F_{ij} [XY] FUNCTIONS OF Zn^{2+} - CITRACONATE - γ -PICOLINE MIXED SYSTEM

$Zn^{2+} = 1.0 \text{ mM}$, $\mu = 0.1$ (KCl), $\text{pH} = 6.6 \pm 0.02$, $\text{Temp.} = 25 \pm 0.5^\circ$,
 $(E_{1/2})_s = -1.10 \text{ V vs SCE}$, $i_d = 48$, γ -Picoline = 0.2 M (Fixed)

Sl. no.	Concn. of citraconate ion M	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	i_d div.	F_{00} [XY]	F_{10} [XY]	F_{20} [XY] $\times 10^{-2}$	F_{30} [XY] $\times 10^{-5}$
1.	0.01	-1.128	39	10.95	-	-	-
2.	0.02	-1.144	37	40.25	1 012.5	-	-
3.	0.03	-1.158	34	130.60	3 686.6	79.55	18.18
4.	0.04	-1.166	32	259.30	5 982.5	117.05	23.01
5.	0.05	-1.172	30	441.80	8 436.0	122.72	19.54

$A' = 20, B' = 2\ 300, C' = 25\ 000, D = 1\ 800\ 000.$

three ternary complexes, viz. $[Zn(Citr)\gamma\text{-Pico}]$, $[Zn(Citr)(\gamma\text{-Pico})_2]$ and $[Zn(Citr)_2(\gamma\text{-Pico})]^{2-}$ with formation constants $\log \beta_{11} = 3.93$, $\log \beta_{12} = 3.95$ and $\log \beta_{21} = 5.00$, respectively.

Values of mixing constant K_M ,

$$K_M = \frac{\beta_{11}}{\sqrt{\beta_{02} \times \beta_{20}}}$$

and stabilisation constant K_s ($\log K_s = \log K_M - \log 2$) were calculated⁹, and found to be $\log K_M = 0.628\ 4$ and $\log K_s = 0.327\ 4$, respectively. The positive nature of these constants clearly indicates that the ternary complexes are slightly more stable than the binary ones. A Scheme, representing the

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